

Artificial neural network-optimized bridgeless Landsman converter for enhanced power factor correction in electric vehicle applications

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ABSTRACT

Electric vehicles (EVs) are gaining popularity globally due to their energy-efficient battery storage systems, low carbon emissions, and eco-friendly operation. By transforming both the transportation and electrical sectors, EVs could create a synergistic relationship that reduces fossil fuel use and improves renewable energy integration. However, this convergence emphasizes the necessity for appropriate power factor correction (PFC) methods, especially in EV battery charging systems, to alleviate supply-end PQ concerns. Use of a bridgeless Landsman converter (BLC), noted for its efficiency and link voltage monitoring, is innovative in this research. A proportional-integral (PI) controller tuned by an artificial neural network (ANN) improves prediction and classification, especially response time. The ANN-based PI controller optimises system performance in real time using adaptive control. Using a hysteresis controller attached to a pulse width modulation (PWM) generator regulates the converter's steady-state switching frequency for accurate and consistent output. The proposed approach reduces harmonic distortions and improves operating efficiency. This comprehensive architecture improves power factor and addresses significant PQ concerns in EV charging infrastructure. Integrating improved control tactics and converter design shows that this approach may support electric car technology developments. MATLAB simulations show that power factor correction (PFC) charges EV batteries quickly and effectively. Findings suggest the technique could increase power quality, system efficiency, and EV uptake.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Electric vehicles (EVs) play a pivotal role in fostering sustainable and efficient transportation by addressing global challenges such as global warming, rising emissions, dwindling fossil fuel reserves, and surging fuel prices [1]. By integrating renewable energy-based power generation and EV technology, these vehicles present a promising solution to these pressing issues. As a viable and sustainable mode of transportation, EVs have garnered significant attention due to their alignment with the goals of reducing carbon footprints and advancing battery technology [2].

The quality of input and output power in EV systems is managed through power factor correction (PFC) techniques. However, conventional PFC methods are hindered by power losses and inadequate handling of large load transients [3]. These limitations can be effectively addressed by integrating PFC techniques with advanced converter systems [4].

Traditional boost converters, while offering high boosting ratios in ideal conditions, are often impractical due to voltage stress and dynamic instability [5]. These challenges necessitate higher-rated switches for reliable operation [6]. Buck-boost converters overcome some limitations by supporting both voltage bucking and boosting, but their discontinuous input current restricts their usability [6], [7]. The Cuk converter improves voltage gain with reduced switching losses and enhanced voltage regulation; however, its static gain is inadequate for low-voltage PV systems, and its inverted output limits its application [8], [9]. Similarly, the single-ended primary-inductor converter (SEPIC) converter offers high gain and a non-inverted output, yet its performance is impeded by significant current ripples, making it unsuitable for high-power interleaved EV chargers [10]-[15].

The Landsman converter, a derivative of the SEPIC and Cuk converters, offers better voltage conversion ratios while maintaining continuous input and output currents, which is ideal for EV battery charging where voltage stability and low current ripple are critical [16]. Though the Landsman converter is a fourth-order nonlinear system, this complexity is advantageous when using artificial neural networks (ANNs) [17]. ANNs can learn and adapt to complex dynamics more effectively than traditional control methods, thus making the higher-order dynamics manageable and optimizable. While 2nd or 3rd order converters are simpler and may have lower switching losses, they lack the flexibility and performance range that the Landsman converter offers under dynamic input/output conditions typical in EV environments [18]-[20]. Its operation is optimized using a closed-loop proportional-integral (PI) controller, which ensures output stability by managing the on-off switching times and improving both static and dynamic system characteristics [21], [22]. The integration of ANNs augments the system's predictive capabilities, leveraging human intelligence to enhance detection and classification efficiency [23].

In this research, a bridgeless Landsman converter is implemented to achieve effective and noiseless operation. The converter's performance is regulated by an ANN-based PI controller, which aids in operational detection and classification. Additionally, a hysteresis controller coupled with a pulse width modulation (PWM) circuit ensures precise switching frequency regulation, leading to enhanced efficiency and reduced power quality issues. This framework underscores the potential of advanced converter and control strategies to address critical challenges in EV charging systems.

2. METHOD

This paper introduces a novel charging technique with improved PFC tailored for battery-operated electric vehicles (BEVs). The proposed method employs a bridgeless Landsman converter designed to minimize losses, enhance efficiency, and achieve higher voltage gain. The integration of an ANN-based PI controller facilitates effective converter control and ensures the transfer of maximum power [24]. Additionally, the controller aids in power detection and operational classification [25]. To predict steady-state switching frequencies and ensure reliable output generation, a hysteresis-regulated PWM generator is utilized. The basic schematic diagram of the proposed methodology is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. ANN based bridgeless Landsman converter for PFC

The proposed ANN based controllers compare the converter's voltage to a reference voltage and process it. A reference current is output by the controller and compared to the converter's current [26]. The hysteresis controller receives this comparison result. The Landsman converter's operation is regulated by the hysteresis controller's output, assuring steady voltage.

2.1. Bridgeless Landsman converter

The suggested method supplies AC mains power to the bridgeless Landsman converter at UPF. The converter has three modes. The voltages across switches S_1 and S_2 are denoted as V_{s1} and V_{s2} , respectively. The currents through inductors L_{L1} and L_{L2} are represented as I_{L11} and I_{L12} , while the currents through the output inductors L_{O1} and L_{O2} are denoted as I_{L01} and I_{L02} , respectively. Figure 2 illustrates the circuit diagram of the bridgeless Landsman converter.

- Mode 1: In this mode, switch S_1 is turned ON, causing capacitor C_1 to discharge and transfer its energy to charge inductor L_{L1} . During mode 1, inductor L_{O1} discharges, contributing to an increase in V_{DC} and I_{L11} , while the voltage across capacitor C_1 decreases. Figure 3 shows the bridgeless Landsman converter circuit in mode 1.
- Mode 2: In this mode, both switches are in the OFF state, allowing the charging of inductor L_{O1} and capacitor C_1 to occur. Additionally, during mode 2, the input inductor L_{L1} discharges, resulting in a rise in the voltage across capacitor C_1 . Figure 4 depicts the circuit configuration of the bridgeless Landsman converter during mode 2 of operation.
- Mode 3: In mode 3, discontinuous conduction causes inductor current discontinuity. The current I_{L11} drops to zero when the inductor L_{L1} discharges fully. In the meantime, capacitor C_1 's voltage drops and the output inductor's current rises. Figure 5 shows the bridgeless Landsman converter circuit in mode 3.

Figure 2. Circuit diagram of Landsman converter

Figure 3. Converter operation in mode 1

Figure 4. Converter operation in mode 2

Figure 5. Converter operation in mode 3

The bridgeless Landsman converter's input voltage is as (1). Here, a maximum supply voltage as V_m and frequency is specified by f_L .

$$\begin{aligned} V_S(t) &= V_m \sin(\omega_L t) \\ &= V_m \sin(2\pi f_L t) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$V_{in} = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\pi} V_S \quad (2)$$

The duty cycle of the converter is calculated as (3).

$$D = \frac{V_{DC}}{V_{in} + V_{DC}} = \frac{V_{DC}}{|V_m \sin(\omega t)| + V_{DC}} \quad (3)$$

The value of inductors L_{O1} and L_{O2} is given as (4) and (5).

$$L_{O1} = L_{O2} = \left(\frac{V_S^2}{P_i} \right) \frac{D}{\Delta i_{f_s}} = \frac{i}{\Delta i_{f_s}} \left(\frac{V_S^2}{P_i} \right) \left(\frac{V_{DC}}{V_{in} + V_{DC}} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$= \frac{i}{\Delta i_{f_s}} \left(\frac{V_{Smin}^2}{P_{max}} \right) \left(\frac{V_{DCmax}}{\sqrt{2}V_{Smin} + V_{DC}} \right) \quad (5)$$

The value of inductors L_{IC1} and L_{IC2} is as (6).

$$L_{IC1} = L_{IC2} = \left(\frac{V_{Smin}^2}{P_{max}} \right) \frac{V_{DCmax}}{2\sqrt{2}V_{Smin}f_s} \left(\frac{V_{DCmax}}{\sqrt{2}V_{Smin} + V_{DCmax}} \right) \quad (6)$$

The value of capacitance C_1 and C_2 is given as (7).

$$C_1, C_2 = \frac{V_{DC}}{\kappa\{V_{DC} + V_{in}\}f_s(V_{DC}^2/P_i)} \left(\frac{V_{DC}}{V_{in} + V_{DC}} \right) \quad (7)$$

The value of capacitance C_D is given as (8).

$$C_D = \frac{P_{min}}{2\omega\Delta V_{DCmin}^2} \quad (8)$$

Bridgeless Landsman converters keep the PF near unity, assuring system stability.

2.2. ANN based PI controller

The introduction of an artificial neural network (ANN) effectively addresses the challenges of non-linear systems, enabling the generation of essential switching signals for the bridgeless Landsman converter. Its self-adaptive nature makes it highly suitable for managing uncertainties, parameter variations, and nonlinearities. ANN is typically utilized for system identification due to its learning and generalization capabilities. In this setup, the reference current required for the operation of the hysteresis controller is generated by the ANN-based PI controller. Figure 6 illustrates the structure of the ANN-based PI controller, where the state generator is provided with a voltage input.

$$V = [V_{DC,LOW}^{ref} \quad V_{DC,LOW}]^T \quad (9)$$

State x_1 and x_2 from the generator are in (10).

$$x_1 = V_e(m), x_2 = \frac{\delta x_1}{\delta m} \quad (10)$$

Equation for output error is calculated as (11).

$$Z(m) = V_o(m) - V_o(m-1) \quad (11)$$

Controlling signals are created by neuron cells in linked groups.

$$V(m) = V(m - 1) + \sum_{k=i}^{ii} W_k(m)a_k(m) \tag{12}$$

System weight is W_k . Hebb's rule updates the neuron's weight, which is in (13).

$$\Delta W_k(m) = F_k(Y(m), a_{k(m)}) \tag{13}$$

For m^{th} moment, the change in weight is given as (14).

$$\Delta W_k(m) = -c \frac{\delta F_k(m)}{\delta W_k(m)} \tag{14}$$

Optimization tunes PI controller settings of $W_k(m)$.

$$I_s < \frac{c_{DC}V_{DC,LOW}^{ref}}{3K_pL_f} \tag{15}$$

$$I_s \leq \frac{V_sK_p}{2R_fK_p+L_fK_i} \tag{16}$$

The source voltage and current are denoted by V_s and I_s , whereas the proportional and integral gain are denoted by K_p and K_i . The PI controller outputs hysteresis controller reference current.

Figure 6. ANN based controller structure

2.3. Hysteresis controlled PWM circuit

Hysteresis PWM control uses inductor current feedback signals for exact outcomes. Instead of adding an inductor winding, the new hysteresis-regulated PWM circuit uses a simple RC network between the comparator and converter outputs. The RC integral circuit creates a triangle voltage from the comparator output when its AC component is added as the comparator input. Notably, converter input voltage does not affect switching frequency.

The controller's transfer process exhibits derivative characteristics, where the coefficient is directly proportional to the time constant of the RC integral circuit. At the switching frequency f_s , if the impedance of the capacitor is lower compared to the resistance R_2 , the controller achieves improved performance.

$$\frac{1}{2\pi f_s C_1} \ll R_2 \tag{17}$$

The switching frequency is given as (18).

$$f_s = \frac{DV_{CP}}{V_H T_C} \tag{18}$$

The hysteresis voltage V_H , duty cycle (D), and time constant T_C are supplied.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research proposes a new charging technique for a battery-operated electric vehicle (BEV) with improved PFC. This technique comprises a bridgeless Landsman converter, ANN based PI controller in addition to hysteresis controller based PWM generator. The entire technique is simulated using MATLAB. The parameter specifications for the bridgeless Landsman converter are given in Table 1.

Current and voltage waveforms of an AC source are depicted in Figure 7. The input AC current first varies from +2.5 A to -2.5 A and then stabilizes between +2 A to -2 A. AC voltage waveforms are stable about 70 V. Figure 8 shows the input AC supply power waveform. The bridgeless Landsman converter receives 50 W to 70 W from 0.6 s. The voltage across capacitor C_1 and C_2 is given in Figures 9(a) and 9(b). The load current is shown in Figure 10(a), and the load voltage waveform is given in Figure 10(b). As illustrated in Figure 11, the proposed control approach using an ANN-based bridgeless Landsman converter achieves a unity power factor, thereby enabling efficient and rapid charging of electric vehicle (EV) batteries.

Table 1. Parameter specifications for the bridgeless Landsman converter

Parameters	Values
Power rating	1 kW
Input AC voltage range (V_{AC})	180 to 270 V
Output DC voltage range (V_{DC})	270 to 330 V
L_{I1}, L_{I2}	1 mH
L_{O1}, L_{O2}	3.7 mH
C_1, C_2	47 μ F
C_O	570 μ F

Figure 7. Input AC source: (a) current waveform and (b) voltage waveform

Figure 8. Input power waveform

Figure 9. Voltage waveforms across the capacitors: (a) voltage across capacitor C_1 , and (b) voltage across capacitor C_2

Figure 10. Converter load waveforms: (a) load current and (b) load voltage

Figure 11. Power factor waveform

4. CONCLUSION

Electric vehicles (EVs) are gaining widespread adoption due to their numerous advantages, including advanced battery storage systems, low carbon emissions, and environmentally friendly operations. This study proposes a rapid and efficient EV battery charging system utilizing a BLC. The inclusion of inductors at both the input and output sides of the converter significantly reduces current ripples, ensuring stable and noiseless operation.

To enhance system performance, an artificial ANN-based PI controller is integrated, enabling quick estimation and precise management of the reference voltage. This hybrid control strategy improves prediction and classification processes, contributing to more reliable converter operation. Additionally, a hysteresis controller is implemented to accurately estimate the steady-state switching frequency, further optimizing the converter's performance. The proposed PFC technique is validated through MATLAB simulations, demonstrating its effectiveness in achieving fast and efficient EV battery charging. The results underscore the potential of the proposed approach to minimize power quality issues, enhance system efficiency, and support the rapid adoption of EV technology.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

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Radhakrishnan Anandhakumar		✓				✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
T. Vijay Muni L. Shanmukha Rao	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓	✓

C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data availability is not applicable to this paper as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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